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Challenges for Implementation of Halal Tourism in the Maldives; Expert's Perspective

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Annotation: *Purpose-* The primary purpose of this study is to recognize the challenges Maldives has in the implementation of Halal tourism in the Maldives from the perspectives of local industry experts. Annually on average tourist arrivals from Middle East; the region which has the most Muslim tourist arrivals are less than 5% of the total annual tourist arrivals and over the years, this figure has not increased and while so, the concept of halal tourism has been recently recognized in the academia, is in need of research to study the gaps and challenges faced when increasing the number of Muslim tourists.

Design- This is a qualitative study and data was gathered from ten local tourism experts (industry and academic experts) via telephone interviews.

Methodology- This paper includes literature from various journal articles, conference proceedings and annual reports in addition to the data collected from phone interviews.

*Findings-*Four themes were identified from the qualitative data collected from respondents such as less awareness of Halal tourism, unsatisfactory control on Halal certification, less research on halal tourism based on the Maldives and less marketing and focus on Muslim tourist segment.

Originality of the research- This study employed primary data collection and this paper is significant as it focuses on Halal tourism by focusing on the challenges there is for the Maldives to implement

Halal tourism in the Maldivian tourism industry, with limited research, this paper will shed light on the challenges of implementation of Halal tourism in the Maldives.

Keywords: Halal Tourism, Muslim Tourists, Industry Experts, Maldivian Tourism Industry, Less Awareness, Unsatisfactory Halal Certification, Less Research, Less Marketing Focus

INTRODUCTION(KIRISH)

Explained by Rahmawati, Oktora, Ratnasari, Ramadania and Darma (2021) Halal tourism is designed to make it more convenient for Muslim tourists to fulfill the obligatory Islamic duties while traveling. According to Hossain and Hosain (2020), Halal tourism is the type of tourism geared for Muslims and at present, Halal tourism has shown a lucrative promise with the concept being spread to even non-Muslim countries such as Russia, Germany, Singapore, United Kingdom and Japan. While Maldives has a well-established conventional tourism industry for the past 40 years, evidently Halal tourism has not been practiced in the resorts/hotels in the Maldives and this has been evident from the tourist arrival figures with Muslim tourists from the Middle East being the least arrival annually with less than 5% of the total tourist arrivals to the Maldives (Maldives Insider, 2019). In addition, there is less research and less promotional activities geared for the Muslim tourists while most of the work has been focused on the European Market resulting in the highest number of tourist arrivals from Europe to the Maldives annually (Maldives Insider, 2019). Increasing the number of Muslim tourist arrivals is crucial to the Maldivian tourism industry as the Maldivian tourism industry is the most contributing to the economy of the Maldives and the Maldives tourism industry recently has been stagnant (Corporate Maldives, 2019). In order to achieve more yield from the tourism industry, diversification of the tourism industry is crucial for the development of the economy and to diversify, tapping into other markets is also important with the Middle East market being the market with the least number of tourist arrivals annually stagnant (Corporate Maldives, 2019).

Therefore, exploring the challenges of implementing Halal tourism in the Maldives would bring light to the challenges that need to be dealt with in order to diversify the tourism industry. The purpose of this paper is to find and explore the challenges present in the implementation of Halal tourist resorts/hotels in the Maldives from the viewpoint of the tourism experts in Maldives. The research problem that is being explored in this study is

“What are the challenges in the Maldives for Maldivian tourism industry to commence Halal tourism?”. Hence, the aim of this study is to recognize the challenges for the Maldives to implement Halal tourism in the Maldives and the data is collected from ten industry and academic experts from the Maldives. While few studies have been conducted to recognize the connection between religiosity and travel in the Maldives, the major challenges for implementation of Halal tourism in the Maldives is yet to be explored and hence, this study attempts to fill this gap of finding what makes it difficult to implement Halal tourism in the Maldives.

History of Halal tourism

Muslims have been travelling for thousands of years ago, in fact, prophets of Islam except for prophet Mohamed (SAW) has been instructed by Allah to travel many places spreading the word of Islam and peace (Saalih Al-Munajjid, 2021). Prophet Ibrahim (AS) was similarly instructed by Allah not to remain in one place but to travel from place to place spreading the word of Islam and to fulfill this instruction prophet Ibrahim (AS) never remained in one place but lived-in temporary tents and travelled as far as he could spreading the word of Islam peace (Saalih Al-Munajjid, 2021). Many other prophets also travelled from one place to another spreading the word of Islam and hence, travelling has been a prominent part of a Muslim’s life starting from thousands of years ago. In the book of Quruan, the word “travel” has been mentioned 27 times while in Quruan travelling has been instructed for many purposes such as for trade & commerce, to gather knowledge, for entertainment and relaxation, for immigration, for science and to learn from other cultures peace (Saalih Al-Munajjid, 2021).

Halal tourism at present

According to Battour (2019), Halal tourism is a subcategory of tourism which is geared to cater for the Muslims while this type of tourism has to have Muslim-friendly facilities that fulfill the needs of Muslim tourists. According to Churiyah, Pratikto, Filianti and Akbar (2020), report compiled by a collaboration of Thomson Reuters and Dinar standard, 2017 ended spending figures of Halal tourism globally amount to US\$ 177 billion and is expected to grow and reach an estimated value of US\$ 274 billion by the year 2023 ended and majority of the Middle East Muslim tourists travel to the European countries. Similarly, Halaltrip (2021) stated that in 2019, Halal tourism accounted for a total 13% of the global tourism industry and is forecasted to grow more in the coming few years. According to Dinar standard (2020), in the year 2019 ended there were over 200 million Muslim tourists who traveled all over the world, and even with the steps back due to Covid-19, Halal tourism is expected to project same or more of what Halal tourism profited by the year 2023. Halaltrip (2021), reports both Muslim and non-Muslim countries which were most traveled among Muslim travelers including Saudi Arabia,

Malaysia, Turkey, Kazakhstan, Egypt, Indonesia, Oman, Iran, UAE and Qatar among the most traveled Muslim countries and Germany, Russia, India, UK and China as the non-Muslim countries most Muslim tourists traveled during 2019 ended.

According to Crescentrating (2020), Crescentrating's faith-based needs model which was developed in the 2018, which include of the things that are most required for the Muslim tourists and according to this model halal food, prayer facilities, water-friendly facilities, and no Islamophobia are the most important Muslim-friendly attributes required by Muslim tourists while those that are good to have but not mandatory are social causes, Ramadhan services and local Muslim experience. In addition, things that are nice to have according to Muslim tourists are recreational facilities with privacy and having no non-halal activities (Crescentrating, 2020). Explained by Abror, Wardi, Trinanda and Patrisia (2019), empirical evidence has shown that there is a significant relationship between halal food and Muslim tourist satisfaction and it was found out that Halal food is one aspect that Muslim tourists pay attention when selecting destinations. According to Rashid, Wangbenmad and Mansor (2020), studies have shown that having prayer facilities in the destinations Muslim tourist travel to has a significant impact on the tourist satisfaction as for a Muslim, performing daily five prayers is mandatory and having the facilities to perform these prayers makes their trip easy. Explained by Hijawi, Abuamoud, Wilkerson and Al Rawabdeh (2019), Muslim tourists have rated having water-friendly washrooms as mandatory service that needs to be available in destinations Muslims travel to because for cleaning and ablution, water is required for Muslims. Zohir and Bouhouili (2020), having Islamophobia in a destination makes the destination unsafe for Muslim tourists and in order to be satisfied with the destination, the destination needs to be welcoming to Muslims despite of any race they came from. According to Noor, Mokhtar, Sharif, Long, Rahman and Wahab (2020), destinations which promote sustainable tourism initiatives such as eco-tourism and tourism with social causes, are found to be an aspect attractive to the Muslim tourists and although not mandatory, Muslim tourists are found to prefer hotels/resorts which promote sustainable tourism. Hardius, Nurdin and Fahadil Amin (2020), having Ramadhan services in the destinations Muslim travel during the month of Ramadhan makes it easy for the Muslims to fast and this aspect is empirically found to satisfy Muslim tourists. According to Rashid, Akbar, Laidin and Muhamad (2019), it is found that for Muslim tourists, having to experience local Muslim life does increase the satisfaction of the Muslim tourists. Vargas-Sanchez and Moral-Moral (2019), stated that having recreational facilities with privacy makes it very comfortable for Muslim tourists to enjoy the recreational services of the hotel/resort easily.

Due to the lucrative nature of Halal tourism, non-Muslim destinations have also started embracing Halal tourism such as Singapore, Thailand and UK and are still developing

more Muslim-friendly options for the Muslim tourists (Pietro, Silvana, Maha and Mohamad, 2019). According to Pradana, Huertas-Garcia and Marimon (2020), Spain has been flooding with Muslim tourists and the Muslim tourist population has been growing as Spain is still developing more and more Muslim-friendly services in the hotels and resorts. Explained by Rehman (2020), countries like Singapore, United Kingdom and Australia has been increasing more hotels and resorts that has Muslim-friendly services due to the increase in Muslim tourists traveling to these countries.

Maldivian tourism industry

According to (Ministry of Tourism, 2019), Maldives commenced conventional tourism in 1972 with the first resort named Kurumbaa village, locally known as “vihamanaafushi” with bed capacity of 280 which still is operation and today has over 106 resorts in operation, all distributed in all atolls of the Maldives. Maldives has over 1000 islands all geographically distributed and separated by reefs, lagoons and sea and this geographical dispersion and land scarcity makes it very challenging to nurture various industries, as a result tourism is the most contributing to the GDP of the Maldives with a direct of 30% (Ministry of Tourism, 2019). Currently Maldives has an operating of 158 tourist resorts, 13 hotels, 594 guesthouses, 133 vessels (safari), 216 dive centers, 397 travel agencies, 14 tour guides and 3 yacht marinas operating all to cater services in the tourism industry (Ministry of Tourism, 2019). From the tourist arrival percentage of 2020 January to 2020 December the number of tourist arrivals from Middle East is 4.7% while the figure has been at 5% or below even during the last 5 years consecutively (Ministry of Tourism, 2019). In addition Maldives has international hospitality brands such as Jumeirah, Four Seasons, Conrad, Clubmed, Soneva, Shangri-la, Adaaran, Dusit Thani, Holliday Inn, Angsana, Sheraton, Constance, Diamonds, W hotels and Cheval Blanc (Ministry of Tourism, 2019).

However, over the last few years, tourism industry of the Maldives has been more stagnant and growth has been stagnant due to less diversification. According to World Bank Group (2019), Maldives is among one of the poorest countries in terms of GDP. Maldives needs diversification of the tourism industry in order to increase its contribution to the GDP. Due to the lack of studies and promotional strategies focused on Muslim tourists, annually Muslim tourists from the Middle east are the segment with the least number of tourists with an annual average of less than 5% of the total tourist arrivals from the Middle east. While few attempts have been made to start a Halal tourist resort in the Maldives, none of the projects have been materialized and as a result, Halal tourism has not started in the Maldives evidently. To start Halal tourism in the Maldives, studies and research has to be done to find the challenges, opportunities and Muslim tourist behavior for Maldives to be able to develop Halal tourism.

Challenges in the development of Halal tourism in the world

According to El-Gohary (2020), due to the fast developing of the world, tourism also keeps changing with tourists being more selective and always searching for destinations that are able to satisfy their travel needs and with the everchanging tourism industry, Halal industry also has its challenges, more recently the pandemic of Coronavirus which started in the year 2020 and due to this pandemic, when destinations opening doors to Muslim tourists, more regulations needs to be developed and implemented and this will require a lot of time. Explained by Bogan and Sariisik (2019), developing Muslim-friendly hotels and resorts should be done under specific and well-defined Halal standards and currently one of the major problems faced by most countries is that there is lack of Halal standards which makes it difficult for hotels and resorts to have a governing benchmark for the Muslim-friendly services being provided in the hotels. Rasul (2019), highlighted that Halal tourism is facing many challenges such as Halal tourism still not being clearly defined and the problems already existing in some societies such as Islamophobia. Moshin, Brochado and Rodrigues (2020), Islamophobia and Halal standards not being correctly defined pose as a challenge in developing Muslim-friendly services in some destinations. Prayag (2020), stated that one of the main problems in developing Halal standards is due to the small body of studies and literature available on the concept of Halal tourism as well as Muslim tourist behavior and with limited research, it is difficult to develop a framework that can monitor and govern Halal practices all over the world. In addition, Prayag (2020), highlighted that most of the empirical studies on Halal tourism has been confined to few countries such as Malaysia and Indonesia, making studies on Muslim behavior on other countries scarce.

Sahabuddin and Agustina (2020), pointed out that national level challenges if implementing Halal tourism in Indonesia include of not being able to do enough promotional and awareness strategies to aware the society about Halal tourism and clearing the negative stigma revolved around Halal tourism. Vandromme (2020), pointed out that civil unrest and political disputes within a country such as Tunisia, developing Halal tourism becomes a challenge as Muslim tourists are reluctant to travel to a destination which has civil unrest and do not feel safe. Meirezaldi (2020) explained that not having a properly defined Halal certification pose as a challenge in running Halal tourism. Highlighted by Wahyuningtiyas and Ramadhan (2020), as well as Mohsin, Brochado and Rodrigues (2020), one major challenge includes of less awareness among the public on Halal tourism and therefore, steps need to be taken in order to increase the awareness. Zakaria and Abdullah (2019) and Ab Talib (2020) argued that having adequate control on Halal certification ensures the consistency of Halal component being provided in Hospitality industry as well. Destiana and Kismartini (2020), as well as

Mashuri (2020) explored the importance of having more research on Halal tourism as destinations are adopting the concept and having less research will make it difficult to learn travel behavior of Muslims. Muskin., Mutmainah, D. N., Sri Sundari., Purwoko, D., Bustang. (2020) and Rozalinda., Nurhasnah., & Andespa, R. (2019) stated the importance of having more marketing activities as a strategy to promote Halal tourism.

METHODOLOGY(METODOLOGIYA)

This paper explores the challenges that are already in the Maldives for the Maldives to implement Halal tourism to its already well-established conventional tourism industry, from the perspectives of tourism experts. Therefore, data will be collected using structured telephone interviews from ten local tourism industry experts from both the management area as well as from academia. The rationale for employing telephone interviews is due to the reason that during COVID-19 lockdown, face-to-face interviews can pose many obstacles such as restrictions to meet face-to-face and therefore most convenient is telephone interviews. In addition to this benefit, telephone interviews also reduce the cost of traveling. The type of data is primary data because data is collected by the researcher for the purpose of this study. Unit of analysis are individuals while time horizon is cross-sectional, meaning interviews are conducted once to each expert. In addition, study setting is natural setting and researcher interference is minimal while the interview questions are adapted.

Interview questions	Source adopted
How long have you been working in the tourism industry/ teaching and studying the tourism industry?	Salleh, Nor, Azmin, Samori and Anas (2019)
How important do you think diversification is for the Maldivian tourism industry and how do you think it will impact?	Priyono (2018) Rasul (2019) Developed for the study
What are the challenges in implementing Halal tourism in the Maldives?	Salleh, Nor, Azmin, Samori and Anas (2019) Jia and Chaozhi (2020) Developed for the study
What are the possible steps that can be taken to tackle these challenges?	Priyono (2018)

	Rasul (2019) Developed for the study
How soon do you think Maldives be ready to commence Halal tourism in the Maldives?	Salleh, Nor, Azmin, Samori and Anas (2019) Developed for the study

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION(NATIJALAR VA MUHOKAMA)

From the qualitative data collection four themes were identified; such as less awareness of Halal tourism, unsatisfactory control on Halal certification, less research on halal tourism based on the Maldives and less marketing and focus on Muslim tourist segment. Respondents highlighted that these four themes have been most recognized challenges in the implementation of Halal tourism in the Maldives.

Theme 1: Less awareness of Halal tourism

According to the respondents Halal tourism being recently recognized in the academia and in the business arena, Maldives also has a long way in getting more familiar with the concept of Halal tourism. Respondents agreed that less awareness programs have been conducted by both the government as well as private organizations to create and increase awareness on the concept of Halal tourism. One of the respondent's opinion was, *"almost all of the programs conducted by the government and by the local resort chains are also confined to only discussing about the conventional tourism we have and ways we can increase the number of tourists, but rarely discuss the revenue we get from Muslim tourists from United Arab Emirates, Qatar, Saudi Arabia, Egypt, Jordan and Lebanon"* (industry expert, 1). Respondents further added that most of the policy makers in the Maldives do not possess enough knowledge about Halal tourism and majority of these policy makers are also unaware on how lucrative Halal tourism is all over the globe and that even non-Muslim countries who realized the potential of the Halal tourism has started Halal tourism with Muslim-friendly services. Another respondent's response was, *"The policy makers of the tourism industry in the Maldives do not have knowledge or experience in Halal tourism so policy makers are not keen on researching and learning to broaden their perspective on how lucrative Halal tourism is all over the world. However, the fact is that if Maldives do want to venture into Halal tourism, we can because we are a Muslim country and we already have many services already in the country which appeal very much to the Muslim tourists such as quality hospitality services and beautiful islands perfect for rejuvenation"* (industry expert, 3) According to the respondents, because there is less awareness on Halal tourism, there has not been policies made up to control and monitor Muslim-friendly services at any point of time the

Maldives implement Halal tourism. Respondents further added that because of less awareness on the concept of Halal tourism, less resorts/hotels have important things such as Qibla noted in the rooms of the resort/hotels. As highlighted by Wahyuningtiyas and Ramadhan (2020), awareness of Halal tourism is still less and ways to increase awareness about Halal tourism is imperative in implementation of Halal tourism at large scale. Mohsin et al., (2020) also emphasized that due to less awareness, awareness about Halal tourism needs to be increased in order to promote Halal tourism.

Theme 2: Clouded judgment of most resort investors

Respondents highlighted another theme as one of the challenges in the implementation of Halal tourism in the Maldives; clouded judgment of most resort owners in the Maldives. Respondents did highlight that a lot of resort owners and investors are reluctant to invest more into Halal tourism based on their clouded perception that Halal tourism is not lucrative, primarily due to lack of knowledge. Another driver for the clouded perception is familiarity, because Maldives since its commencement has been catering for the conventional tourism and Halal tourism being a recently commercialized segment, the uncertainty that accompanies investing in a novel segment also plays to the reluctance of the resort investors in the Maldives including the local investors as well. Because Halal tourism comes with aspects such as seclusion and gender segregation, investors have a perception that developing a Sharia-compliant resort could be a project difficult to materialize, again due to lack of knowledge on the segment. In addition, respondents underlined that in conventional tourism, alcohol generates a handsome profit which is completely absent in Halal tourism and for investors, when there is any aspect of a forecast of a lesser profit margin, they see the options as more riskier than lucrative.

Theme 3: Less research on Halal tourism based on the Maldives

Another theme discussed by the respondents as one of the challenges in implementation of Halal tourism in the Maldives is availability of research on the Muslim travel behavior and Halal tourism based on the case of the Maldives. Respondents discussed that while tourism ministry of the Maldives conducts quarterly surveys to learn about tourists, these studies are mostly based on the markets which brings in most tourists such as the European Market and that there are few researches conducted in the Maldives to learn the Muslim travel behavior, Muslim tourist satisfaction and ways to create Muslim tourist loyalty. A respondent with academic background on Halal tourism added, *“When I started doing my research on Halal tourism based on the Maldives, I found out that there has not been such a research done before and even today less research is available on Muslim travel behavior and Muslim tourist satisfaction based in the Maldives. I feel, for the industry to really satisfy a Muslim tourist, their travel behavior and the type of services that appeal to them the most needs*

to be recognized, for such services to be implemented in the tourism industry of the Maldives" (academic expert, 2). Most of the studies and research conducted by independent researchers and the government has been mostly focusing on learning the travel behavior and tourist satisfaction of tourists from regions such as the Europe. According to the respondents, having less research especially based on the case of the Maldives makes it difficult for the tourism industry to gear and develop services that appeal most to the Muslim tourists hence, availability of the Muslim-friendly services is less in the resorts/hotels of the Maldives. This is one challenge explained by Destiana and Kismartini (2020) highlighting the importance of having more research to learn more about Halal tourism if destinations are to adopt Halal tourism. Mashuri (2020) also explained that having more research is important to explore the concept of Halal tourism as more destinations have implemented Halal concept to the hospitality and other industries.

Theme 4: Less marketing and focus on Muslim tourism segment

The last theme identified and discussed by the respondents is Maldives having less focus on the Muslim tourist segment. According to the figures of tourist arrivals, Muslim tourists from Muslim-majority regions such as Middle east region have been showing the least percentage and this is because almost all the marketing strategies so far has been focused in the Maldives to attract and retain tourists from the western regions and Europe. One of the respondent elaborated, *"Maldives is very active in participating in trade shows in European countries but, less participation is seen in Middle Eastern countries despite the fact that travel authorities found out that Muslim tourists are the biggest spenders. Maldives does have started to engage a little bit more than they did before in promotional activities of Maldivian tourism sector in Gulf countries but I feel we need to do more as Middle East has the potential to become one of the most contributing segment for the tourism in the Maldives"* (industry expert, 6). Respondents agreed that Maldives participate in many tourism trade shows in a lot of European countries while Maldives rarely participate in the tourism trade shows being held in the Middle east countries. In addition, respondents highlighted that even in the tourism strategic market plans, focus on the Middle east segment or the Muslim tourists is less with most of the marketing costs spend on promoting tourism in the western and European market. Muskin et al., (2020) have expressed on this challenge stating that more marketing activities is important for the promotion of Halal tourism. Rozalinda et al., (2019) also stated that having more marketing activities can promote Halal tourism in new platforms and can make the concept more universal.

CONCLUSION

Due to a limited research as well as knowledge of Halal tourism, there are a lot of negative perceptions among the investors that Halal tourism will not be as lucrative as the conventional tourism. Four themes were identified from the qualitative data collected from respondents such as less awareness of Halal tourism, clouded perception of resort investors,, less research on halal tourism based on the Maldives and less marketing and focus on Muslim tourist segment. With Halal tourism being a recently recognized concept commercially and academically, Maldives is fairly new to the aspects of Halal tourism and what constitutes Halal tourism. There is also less research conducted to learn Halal tourism extensively and hence, research based in the Maldives is very less. Because traditionally Maldives started conventional tourism and still has been focusing on marketing the Maldives mostly in the European and Western markets with very little focus on promoting the Maldives in the markets where majority of the Muslims come from; Middle East. In this study, qualitative data was collected via telephone interviews from ten tourism industry experts and hence, this paper only examined the challenges of implementation of Halal tourism in the Maldives from the perspectives of industry experts. While four major themes were recognized this paper has not attempted to study each of the theme in detail and hence, future researches can be conducted to study each of themes in depth.

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